

Saint Achillios Basilica, Prespes

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The basilica dedicated to Saint Achillios († 330) is located on the homonymous island of Prespes, in north-west Greece (western Macedonia). It was suggested that it was built after 983 or 986 by the Bulgarian Tsar Samuel for housing the relics of Larissa's patron Saint Achillios, that Samuel took when he had conquered the city. However, more recently it was pointed out that the excavated elements bear no evidence that could support connection with Tsar Samuel. Instead, an array of evidence bespeaks connection with another person, an ecclesiastical of high rank, the bishop of Ohrid Theofrastos who rebuilt the basilica around 1045, following its destruction by the Alamans. The 10th-century basilica was built on the site of an earlier church, most probably of the 6th century. For a short period it was the seat of the Patriarchate of Bulgaria, following its transfer from Edessa. After the area was reconquered by the Byzantines in 1018 and until the first decades of the 15th century, the church served as the seat of the Bishopric of Ohrid. Saint Achillios to whom the basilica is dedicated was born in Cappadocia. He has held the metropolitan seat of Larissa for 35 years, while he was one of the bishops who have participated in the First Council of Nicaea of 325. The Saint has sensed his death requested the preparation of the sarcophagus in which he was going to be buried. His Vita mentions that his cult was forgotten and that his lost relics were rediscovered through divine revelation 300 years later. His cult developed from the 9th century onwards, while it gained widespread popularity in the 10th century, most probably because of the transfer of his relics to Prespes. The timber-roofed, three-aisled basilica with narthex is preserved today in a ruinous state. The central nave ends at the semi-circular sanctuary with the synthronon. The prothesis and the diakonikon have a cross-in-square plan and they are covered by cylindrical domes. The floor is covered by stone slabs. In the diakonikon was constructed a tomb, probably the one that hosted the relics of Saint Achillios. In the south aisle there are four more tombs, in which very remarkable finds were discovered, such as a piece of a 10th-century silk gilded cloth with eagles, bespeaking the high rank of the individual to whom it belonged. A tripartite structure of funerary nature, adjacent to the southern wall was added in the late-byzantine period. The entire area south and west of the basilica was used as a cemetery from the 12th to the beginning of the 15th century. The basilica has seven doorways, while the sanctuary was separated from the main church by a presbytery barrier made of marble. The few fragments of the monument's fresco decoration belong to two distinct phases, each corresponding to the restoration works that have taken place. The aniconic decoration of the apse's conch belongs to the first decades of the 11th century. More precisely, between the eighteen red arches painted above the synthronon are inscribed in Greek letters the seats of the bishops who belonged to the Archdiocese of Ohrid. The figures of the saints, the Virgin Mary and an angel were painted in the 12th century (second phase). The frescoes in question were detached from the walls of the basilica and were transferred to the Museum of Florina, where they are currently exhibited. The frescoes of the second phase find their closest stylistic parallels to the 12th-century frescoes of the monuments of the city of Kastoria, also in north-west Greece (western Macedonia).

Date Range: 900 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Saint Achillios basilica

Region tags: Greece

Basilica of Saint Achillios, on the homonymous island in Prespes, Greece

Status of Participants:

- ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Gouloulis, S. “Οικοδομικές Και Εικονογραφικές Παρατηρήσεις Στον Άγιο Αχίλλιο Πρέσπας.” In Το Αρμολόϊ. Τιμητικός Τόμος Στον Καθ. Αργύρη Πετρονώτη, P. Androudis and D. Drakoulis. Thessaloniki, 2021.
- Source 2: Moutsopoulos, N. Η Βασιλική Του Αγίου Αχιλλίου Στην Πρέσπα. Ένα Μνημείο Κιβωτός Της Τοπικής Ιστορίας. Thessaloniki, 1999.
- Source 3: Moutsopoulos, N. “Ανασκαφή Βασιλικής Αγίου Αχιλλείου Μικράς Πρέσπας,” Πρακτικά της εν Αθήναις Αρχαιολογικής Εταιρείας, 122 (1967).

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: http://odysseus.culture.gr/h/2/gh251.jsp?obj_id=1768
- Source 1 Description: Description of the basilica of Saint Achillios in Prespes by the Ministry of Culture of Greece
- Source 2 URL: <https://youtu.be/k4ijqw8-5nE>
- Source 2 Description: 3D reconstruction of the basilica of Saint Achillios in Prespes

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Type of excavation:

- Scientific

Years of excavation:

- Year range: 1965-1969 and 1996-1998

Name of excavation

- Official or descriptive name: Excavation of the Basilica of Saint Achillios of Prespes

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Body of water (as distinct from source)

– Other [specify]: Lake

Notes: The basilica is built on an island in Great Prespes

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– No

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Yes

Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

– No

Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– No

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

Specify

– King or emperor

– Other [specify]: It was suggested that it was built after 983 or 986 by the Bulgarian Tsar Samuel for housing the relics of Larissa's patron Saint Achillios, that Samuel had taken when he had conquered the city

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– No

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Yes

Specify

– Other [specify]: It was suggested that it was built for housing the relics of Larissa's patron Saint Achillios, that Tsar Samuel had taken when he had conquered the city

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Yes

Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:

– Yes

Notes: Christian Orthodox. It was suggested that it was built for housing the relics of Larissa's patron Saint Achillios, that Tsar Samuel had taken when he had conquered the city

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Other [specify]: It was suggested that it was built for housing the relics of Larissa's patron Saint Achillios, that Tsar Samuel had taken when he had conquered the city

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– No

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Sand

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Clay

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Plaster

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– Yes

↳ Wood

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Grass

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– I don't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Pigments and binding materials for the mural decoration

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– I don't know

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– No

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– No

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– No

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– No

Notes: Archangels

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

Notes: Saints and Virgin Mary

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

Notes: The sculptural decoration includes also animals

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– No

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– Yes

↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– No

↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Depictions with symbolic meaning

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– No

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– Yes

↳ Type

–'True' fresco

–Secco

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

– Yes

Notes: Among the depicted saints is also Saint Achillios, to whom the basilica is dedicated

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: Motifs with symbolic character

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– No

Notes: Between the eighteen red arches painted above the synthronon are inscribed in Greek letters the seats of the bishops who belonged to the Archdiocese of Ohrid. There is another inscription at the base of the dome of the apse

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative

[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

Notes: Between the eighteen red arches painted above the synthronon are inscribed in Greek letters the seats of the bishops who belonged to the Archdiocese of Ohrid. There is another inscription at the base of the dome of the apse

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– No

↳ Other type of decoration:

– No

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

- ↳ Eyes (stylized or not)
 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)
 - No
- ↳ Portrayals of afterlife
 - No
- ↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)
 - Yes
 - Notes: Cross, fountains, trees, birds
- ↳ Humans
 - Yes
 - Notes: Saints and Virgin Mary, the mother of Christ
- ↳ Supernatural narratives
 - No
- ↳ Human narratives
 - No
- ↳ Other [Specify]
 - Other [specify]: There are no narrative scenes

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: The monument is not a tomb. However, it contains tombs, while its exterior was used as a cemetery

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Notes: There are no grave goods present. Yet, very remarkable finds were found in the tombs of the basilica during excavations

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– Yes

Notes: The tombs in the interior of the basilica

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Notes: The area around the monument was used as a cemetery

↳ Family tomb/crypt:

– No

↳ Domestic context:

Interred beneath floors of house, or in areas of domestic activity

– No

Other

–Other [specify]: The tombs in the interior of the basilica were formal ones. The area around the monument was used as a cemetery

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– No

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– No

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– No

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

Is it required:

– Yes

Notes: The monument is actually in ruinous state

Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– No

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Yes

Notes: The 11th Ephorate of Byzantine Antiquities of the Hellenic ministry of Culture and Sports

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: The monument is maintained by experts such as archaeologists, architects, civil engineers etc.

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Notes: The monument is in ruinous state and so it is not functioning. However, among the visitors of the place might be also pilgrims

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Are festivals present:

– No

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals who's primary duties within a population group are not concerned

with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– No

Notes: The monument is no longer functioning, so it is preserved by the 11th Ephorate of Byzantine Antiquities of the Hellenic Ministry of Culture and Sports.

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Notes: The monument is no longer functioning

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Notes: The 11th Ephorate of Byzantine Antiquities of the Hellenic Ministry of Culture and Sports is in charge of the monument

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Bibliography

General References

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Reference: Saint Achillios Basilica, Prespes, Miljković-Peppek, P.. “Les Fresques De L’église Desaint Achille À Prespa”, Vol. Αρμός, τιμητικός τόμος στον καθηγητή Ν. Μουτσόπουλο. Thessaloniki: University of Thessaloniki, 1991.

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